

A Study on the Technological Spillover Effect of China's OFDI in Africa

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Abstract: This article presents a comprehensive analysis of China's outward foreign direct investment (OFDI) in Africa, examining its economic impact and technology spillover effects. Drawing on a review of relevant literature, the study systematically explores the influence of China's OFDI on technological progress and efficiency in the selected African countries. Using panel data from 29 African countries over the period 2004-2019, this article computes the total factor productivity of the African countries and then empirically analyzes the Chinese OFDI technological spillover effect. The results demonstrate a significant and positive impact of China's OFDI on technology use and advancement in these countries. The study's conclusion summarizes the key findings and offers important policy recommendations. Overall, this research contributes to the ongoing discourse on China's role in Africa's economic development and enhances our understanding of the factors influencing China's outbound investment decisions.

Keywords: China's outward foreign direct investment; Technology spillover effects; Total factor productivity, Africa

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1. Introduction

In recent years, due to the rapid development over the past three decades, China has transitioned from being a destination for foreign direct investment (F.D.I.) to becoming a major source of F.D.I. In particular, since China's accession to the WTO in 2001, its economic interactions with countries around the world, including African nations, have significantly accelerated. The economic and trade collaboration between China and Africa, grounded in their deepening ties, commenced during the 1950s. China, being the largest developing nation globally, has a robust mutually beneficial association with Africa, which harbors the highest concentration of developing countries on the continent. In the 21st century, the launch of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (F.O.C.A.C.) marked a further strengthening of China-Africa relations and has propelled their economic and trade cooperation to become increasingly close. FOCAC provides both sides with a unique and genuine opportunity to establish a relationship that is mutually beneficial, respectful, and based on equality, and that is in line with the long-term interests of both parties. The fifth FOCAC summit held in Beijing in 2012, which was attended by leaders from 42 African countries, received high attention from the international community.

Currently, developing countries have become important sources of foreign direct investment for other emerging nations. The share of developing countries in global FDI outflows increased from 7.6% in 2000 to 41.2% in 2018. During

the same period, the share of their FDI stock increased from 9.3% to 24.3% (UNCTAD 2020).¹ Compared to FDI from developed countries, the increase in FDI from emerging economies provides an additional option for other developing countries. Against the backdrop of the “Going Global” strategy, China’s outward foreign direct investment has experienced rapid growth. Most of the existing research focuses on the impact of China’s O.F.D.I on Africa’s economic growth or the challenges faced by Chinese O.F.D.I in Africa, but there has been little investigation into the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa. After many years of development, China has advantages in advanced technology and management experience. Chinese investment in Africa not only includes capital but also encompasses technology, management expertise, and relevant information, which may have technology spillover effects on Africa. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews previous studies. Section 3 describes the development status of Chinese OFDI in Africa. Section 4 describes the methodology used, model specification, and data description. The empirical results and discussion are presented in Section 5, before concluding the paper in Section 6.

2. Literature review

Foreign direct investment from emerging economies has shown a certain development trend during this century, and China is one representative example of this phenomenon. China’s direct investment in Africa has been found to contribute to the growth of African countries’ GDP (Weisbrod and Whalley, 2012; Michael, 2017)^[1, 2]. The majority of Chinese investment projects in Africa have contributed to the economic and social development of these countries (Liu and Huang, 2012)^[3]. Donou-Adonsou and Lim (2018)^[4] studied the contribution of Chinese OFDI to Africa’s GDP and compared it with Africa’s traditional economic partners, including the United States, France, and Germany. They found that Chinese OFDI has to some extent increased Africa’s income. Additionally, it was explored whether the new relationship between China and Africa has somehow changed the existing relationship between Africa and its traditional partners. This impact was only significant for the United States and Germany. Liu (2020)^[5] conducted an empirical analysis using panel data from 38 African host countries from 2006 to 2017, and through fixed-effects models, found that the contribution of Chinese OFDI was 0.023%, lower than that of other traditional economic partners. Miao et al. (2021)^[6] used data on China’s FDI in 44 African countries based on the two-step system GMM estimation method using data from 2003 to 2017. The study found that Chinese foreign direct investment has a positive impact on Africa’s economic growth and is beneficial to improving the overall level of African countries. Among many countries investing in Africa, China is the only one that significantly and noticeably promotes overall economic growth in African countries. Furthermore, China’s OFDI makes significant contributions to these countries to attract and utilize foreign investment (Zhang 2021)^[7].

The literature has extensively debated the key determinants shaping Chinese investment in Africa. Given the multifaceted nature of these drivers, this study endeavors to systematically examine these factors. Numerous scholars underscore the impact of the host country’s investment environment on FDI activities, particularly the role of “political risk.” However, the absence of a unified definition of “political risk” among international scholars has led to a lack of consensus on the determinants of “political risk” in the context of China’s OFDI in Africa. It is generally believed that “political risk” refers to the negative impact on the operations of most multinational corporations due to policies or actions taken by the government for internal or external reasons of the host country (Yang, 2019)^[8]. Fan’s (2017)^[9] analysis revealed that the main determinant of Chinese OFDI in Africa is political stability. Conversely, Yuan and Ji’s (2020)^[10] analysis of 34 African countries from 2005 to 2017 found that the higher the anti-corruption rate, government efficiency, institutional quality, and legal system of African countries, the less favorable the environment for Chinese OFDI entry. In addition, the research conclusions indicate that China seems to be more willing to accept and manage financial risks when investing in relatively underdeveloped African countries, in other words, Chinese investors are more likely to

¹ <https://unctad.org/topic/investment/investment-statistics-and-trends>

engage in investment opportunities in these countries despite the higher financial risks involved compared to more developed African nations. Finally, frequent terrorist activities, severe corruption, and lagging infrastructure development in Africa are also key determinants (Wu and Meng, 2017) ^[11].

In recent years, research on China’s direct investment in Africa has focused on the impact on economic growth, investment risk analysis, and the analysis of investment motives and influencing factors. Few studies have explored the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa. This study will combine the specific situation of China’s direct investment in African countries and conduct research on the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment through empirical analysis, supplementing the relevant literature in this field.

3. Development Status of Chinese OFDI in Africa

3.1. Development Path of China’s OFDI in Africa

After the establishment of the People’s Republic of China in 1949, the only economic entities in Africa that initially engaged in economic and trade cooperation with China were the Arab Republic of Egypt and the Kingdom of Morocco (An, 2008)^[12]. Currently, China has established economic and trade cooperation with over 50 countries and regions in Africa, signed bilateral trade agreements with more than 40 countries, established bilateral economic and trade joint committees with 35 countries, and signed bilateral encouragement and protection of investment agreements with 28 African countries (Chen and Zhao, 2007)^[13]. The Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), established in 2000, is considered an effective platform for strengthening China’s relations with African countries and establishing long-term stable partnerships. Over the past eight years or so, not only have economic relations between China and many African countries developed rapidly, but China has also become the most important trading partner for these African countries.

In addition, Africa has consistently benefited from a substantial influx of foreign direct investment from China². China’s direct investment in Africa has experienced a remarkable surge in the 21st century, as depicted in Figure 1. The stock of China’s direct investment in Africa increased 94-fold over 15 years (2003-2018), rising from 500 million US dollars to 46.103 billion US dollars.

Fig. 1: The stock of China’s direct investment in Africa (billion US dollars) from 2003 to 2019

Source: Compiled based on the “Statistical Bulletin of China’s Outward Foreign Direct Investment 2003 -2020” released by the Chinese Ministry of Commerce.

Since 2003, the annual influx of foreign direct investment from China into Africa (also referred to as “OFDI” in official Chinese reports) has been steadily increasing. China’s OFDI into Africa surged from 75 million US dollars in 2003 to 2.7 billion US dollars in 2019. There has been a discernible trend in the flow of IFDI into the African region from

²From: <https://doc-research.org/2018/09/chinas-approach-to-africa/>

2003 to 2019, as the FDI from China surpassed that from the United States in 2012, due to the gradual decline in the flow of foreign direct investment to Africa since 2009. Furthermore, the peak of capital inflow was reached in 2008, amounting to 5.5 billion US dollars, as a result of the Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC) acquiring a 20% stake in Standard Bank of South Africa (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: The FDI inflows into Africa from China and the United States from 2003 to 2019 (billion US dollars)

Source: Compiled based on the “Statistical Bulletin of China’s Outward Foreign Direct Investment 2020” and the U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis.

3.2. Evolution of Chinese OFDI in African Sectors:

As analyzed in the previous section, the importance of Chinese FDI in African countries continues to strengthen. China has invested directly in 50 African countries and is increasingly diversifying beyond the primary sector. China’s OFDI in Africa is transitioning from the mining sector to the construction sector (see Figure 3).

Fig. 3: From 2013 to 2020, the top four industries in which China invested directly in Africa (in billion US dollars)

Source: Compiled based on the “Statistical Bulletin of China’s Outward Foreign Direct Investment” released by the Ministry of Commerce of China from 2014 to 2021.

The lack of infrastructure between African cities is one of the major issues plaguing the African economy, leading to a lack of connectivity between rural and urban areas and limited opportunities. The “Belt and Road Initiative” proposed by China in 2013 has garnered global attention as it aims to connect vast regions of the world through land and maritime infrastructure corridors. Although only three African economies, Egypt, Djibouti, and Kenya, are part of the Belt and Road Initiative in the early stage, China’s investment projects in Africa have consistently aligned with the plan and objectives of the initiative (Raphael and Zhao, 2016)^[14]. As shown in Figure 3, the construction and mining sectors have the largest share and number of Chinese capital investment projects (averaging 29.23% and 24.34% respectively from 2013 to 2020). By the end of 2020, China’s investment stock in the African construction sector had grown from \$6.84 billion to \$15.15 billion, accounting for 34.9% of China’s FDI in Africa. In addition to construction, mining, manufacturing, and finance, China’s direct investments in Africa also include commercial services, scientific research, wholesale and retail, agriculture, and real estate.

4. Methodology

This paper will empirically analyze the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in African countries using econometric models, specifically examining their impact on the total factor productivity, technological progress, and technical efficiency of African countries. Due to the official data statistics on China’s direct investment in Africa starting from 2003, this article chooses a time period from 2004 to 2019. Among the 54 African countries, 29 countries are selected in this paper, including the Republic of Angola, the Republic of Botswana, the Republic of Côte d’Ivoire, the Republic of Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the Republic of the Congo, the Democratic People’s Republic of Algeria, the Arab Republic of Egypt, the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, the Gabonese Republic, the Republic of Ghana, the Republic of Kenya Kingdom of Morocco, Republic of Madagascar, Republic of Mali, Republic of Mozambique, Islamic Republic of Mauritania, Republic of Malawi, Republic of Namibia, Republic of Niger, Federal Republic of Nigeria, Republic of Zimbabwe.

4.1. Modeling and Variable Selection

4.1.1. Benchmark Model

Grossman and Helpman (1991)^[15] believe that international trade and FDI, as important channels for international technology spillovers, can encourage host countries to absorb the advanced technology and management level of multinational corporations or enterprises, thereby promoting the improvement of total factor productivity. Based on the theory of new economic growth, Coe and Helpman (1995)^[16] constructed a basic model of cross-border technology spillover effects, which became the basic model for subsequent scholars to conduct in-depth research (referred to as the C-H model); Lichtenberg and Pottelsberghe made certain improvements to the L-P model in 1998 and 2001^[17, 18] Within the framework of its model, this paper modifies the model used by Razzaq et al^[19] and constructs the following benchmark model:

$$MTFP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SFDI_{it} + \sum_{k=2}^n \beta_k X_{it}^k + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{1}$$

Where i represents the African countries, t represents the corresponding year. $MTFP$ is the dependent variable as total factor productivity. β_0 represents the constant term; $SFDI$ represents the foreign R&D capital stock obtained by African countries from China’s OFDI activities in Africa. X_{it}^k represents the k^{th} control variable. β_1 and β_k is the coefficient before the variables; γ_i is a fixed effect of the host country that is unobservable and does not change over time; μ_t the time effect; ε_{it} It represents the random error term.

Total factor productivity is the result of the combined effect of improving practical technical efficiency and technological progress. Therefore, in order to further analyze the impact of technology spillover effects brought by China’s

OFDI on the technological progress (TC) and technology utilization efficiency (EC) of African countries, this article extends model (1) to the following two models:

$$MTC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SFDI_{it} + \sum_{k=2}^n \beta_k X_{it}^k + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{2}$$

$$MEC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SFDI_{it} + \sum_{k=2}^n \beta_k X_{it}^k + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3}$$

4.1.2. Variable selection and calculation methods

The dependent variable *MTFP*: As the Malmquist index calculates the rate of change of total factor productivity relative to the previous year, in the subsequent empirical analysis, the method of Liu et al. (2016)^[20] is used to multiply the rate of change of total factor productivity with the first year as the base period, obtaining the total factor productivity rate of change index from 2004 to 2019; The calculation formula is:

$$MTFP_{it} = TFP_{it} \cdot TFP_{it-1} \tag{4}$$

Where *TFP_{it}* represents the total factor productivity index of the African country *i* calculated using the D.E.A method in year *t*, which is equal to 1 in the first year of the data sample (MTC and MEC are the same).

The core explanatory variable *SFDI*: In order to estimate the technology spillover effects brought by China's OFDI, this article uses the L-P model calculation method, which takes the R&D capital stock of the investing country as a potential stimulus factor for the host country's technology.

$$SFDI_{it} = \frac{FDI_{it}}{K_{ct}} \cdot RD_{ct} \tag{5}$$

Where *FDI_{it}* Indicates China's direct investment stock in African countries in the t-th period. This article refers to the research of Razzaq et al.^[19] and selects China's stock of direct investment in Africa, mainly because the stock is the accumulation of flow and China's direct investment in Africa has been concentrated in infrastructure construction in recent years, so the stock will more effectively reveal long-term impacts. *K_{ct}* is China's domestic fixed capital stock in period t, and this article uses the perpetual inventory method to calculate it. $K_{ct} = K_{ct-1}(1 - \delta_{cap}) + I_t$. Where *K_{ct-1}* is the capital stock of the previous period δ_{cap} is the depreciation rate of material capital, calculated using the method proposed by Zhang et al.^[21] and other researchers (Yue, 2008; Liu and Huang, 2015; Zhao and He, 2019)^[22-24], uniformly using 9.6%; *I_t* is the current investment amount, which is the total amount of capital formation for the year. In the calculation, it is converted to a constant price based on the 2000 base period price index. *RD_{ct}* represents China's domestic R&D capital stock in the t-th period. Similarly, this article uses the perpetual inventory method to calculate it. The calculation formula is: $RD_{ct} = RD_{ct-1}(1 - \delta_{rd}) + S_t$ Where *RD_{ct}* and *RD_{ct-1}* represents the domestic R&D capital stock of China's t-th and t-1 periods; δ_{rd} represents the depreciation rate of R&D capital, which is usually considered to be higher than the depreciation rate of material capital. This article adopts a uniform rate of 15% based on Liu and Huang (2015)^[23]; *S_t* represents the current amount of research and experimental expenses. In the text, the price index of 2000 is used as the base period, and the annual expenses are converted to 2000 prices by excluding price factors.

Other explanatory variables include the Human Capital Index *HUMAN*: a human capital index calculated based on years of education and educational returns. The index and calculation method are sourced from the PWT 9.0 (Penn World Table) database by Feenstra et al. (2015)^[25]. Many studies have fully demonstrated the close relationship between human capital and total factor productivity. This article draws on the methods of Liu and Huang (2015)^[23] and incorporates human capital into the model. Human capital can help countries develop technology and promote economic development, thereby enhancing their ability to absorb advanced technologies brought by foreign investment.

The technology gap between African countries and China **TGAP**: Drawing on the research of Wang et al.^[26] This variable is measured using the following formula: $TGAP_{it} = \frac{Output_{ct}}{Output_{it}}$, here $Output_{ct}$ represents the productivity of

China’s labor force³ in year t, $Output_{it}$ It represents the labor productivity of the i-th host country in year t. This variable is also a factor that affects the technology spillover effects brought about by investing in the home country’s OFDI.

Economic openness **OPEN**: Using the sum of African countries’ exports and imports divided by their gross domestic product, the calculation formula is: $OPEN = \frac{X_{it}+M_{it}}{GDP_{it}}$, where X_{it} represents the export value of country i in year t,

M_{it} represents the import amount of country i in year t, GDP_{it} is the gross domestic product of country i in year t.

Industrial structure **INDUS**: measured by the percentage of industrial added value to GDP. The different industrial structures in different countries or regions can also lead to differences in their technological levels. According to the research of Zhang and Zhao (2011)^[27], only when the industrial structure of a host country develops to a certain level, will there be positive spillover space for advanced technologies brought about by foreign direct investment. Therefore, this article also incorporates the variable industrial structure into the model.

Government Consumption Expenditure **GOVC**: This variable is used as a proxy for distortions caused by non-productive government expenditure and related taxation, as well as changes in fiscal policy stance. This factor is one of the prerequisites for the technology spillover effect brought about by foreign direct investment. Therefore, this article introduces its variables into the model as control variables. The index and calculation method are sourced from the PWT 9.0 (Penn World Table) database by Feenstra et al. (2015)^[25].

The stability of currency **STAB**: This index mainly consists of four aspects: currency growth rate, inflation rate, deviation degree of optimal inflation rate, and degree of freedom to exchange foreign currency. This article is based on the research conclusion of Chen and Liu (2015)^[28], which suggests that deflation will reduce investment and be detrimental to economic development. Therefore, in order to analyze the role of monetary factors in total factor productivity growth, as well as technological progress and efficiency, this article introduces the robustness of currency as a control variable. This data is published annually by the Fraser Institute of Canada. Table 1 summarizes the specific meanings and data sources of these variables in this article.

Table 1: Basic information and data sources of variables

Variable	Code	Description	Source
Dependent	<i>MTFP</i>	Total Factor Productivity	Index Calculated from DEA-Malmquist method
	<i>MTC</i>	Technological change	World Bank and OECD National Accounts Database
	<i>MEC</i>	Technological Efficiency	
Core independent	<i>SFDI</i>	Technological spillover from China’s OFDI	Statistical Bulletin on China’s Foreign Direct Investment China Bureau of Statistics
Controls	<i>HUMAN</i>	Human Capital	Penn World Table ⁴
	<i>TGAP</i>	Technology Gap	WDI
	<i>OPEN</i>	Economic openness	WDI and UNCTAD

³ The productivity of labor is: $Output_{it} = \frac{GDP_{it}}{L_{it}}$, where L is the number of laborers in country i.

⁴ From: <https://www.ggd.net/pwt>

<i>INDUS</i>	Industrial structure	WDII
<i>GOVC</i>	Government Consumption Expenditure	Penn World Table
<i>STAB</i>	The stability of currency	Economic Freedom of the World, EFW index ⁵

Source: Compiled by the author.

5. Regression result and discussion

Firstly, we took the logarithm of the core explanatory variable *SFDI* to reduce heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and multicollinearity issues. In addition, we used the lag of one year in *lnSFDI* here because it represents the domestic R&D capital stock in Africa transformed from China’s direct investment in Africa. *HUMAN* is also used with a lag of one period because it represents the years of education that the worker has completed. These two variables reflect the impact of the previous period’s changes on the current total factor productivity, technological progress, and technological efficiency. Moreover, it addresses the potential reverse causality issues (one of the main endogeneity issues in econometrics). This article sets the econometric benchmark model as:

$$MTFP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln SFDI_{it-1} + \beta_2 \text{ }_{it-1} + \beta_3 TGAP_{it} + \beta_4 OPEN_{it} + \beta_5 INDUS_{it} + \beta_6 GOVC_{it} + \beta_7 STAB_{it} + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{6}$$

$$MTC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln SFDI_{it-1} + \beta_2 HUMAN_{it-1} + \beta_3 TGAP_{it} + \beta_4 OPEN_{it} + \beta_5 INDUS_{it} + \beta_6 GOVC_{it} + \beta_7 STAB_{it} + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{7}$$

$$MEC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln SFDI_{it-1} + \beta_2 HUMAN_{it-1} + \beta_3 TGAP_{it} + \beta_4 OPEN_{it} + \beta_5 INDUS_{it} + \beta_6 GOVC_{it} + \beta_7 STAB_{it} + \gamma_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{8}$$

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistical results of the variables in this article. It can be seen that there is a significant difference between the minimum and maximum values of some variables, such as the proxy variables for the technology gap between African countries and China, which are 0.120 and 24.663, respectively; The robustness of the currency is 0 and 9.498, respectively, with the minimum value of 0 being from 2004 to 2007 in the Republic of Zimbabwe. Due to the Zimbabwean government ceasing to declare official inflation that year, it is difficult to measure Zimbabwe’s hyperinflation statistics. This article studies the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa, namely the impact of China’s OFDI on the total factor productivity of African countries. Firstly, fixed effects and random effects models were used to estimate the changes in total factor productivity (*MTFP*), technological progress (*MTC*), and technological efficiency (*MEC*) of African countries. Based on the estimation results, Hausman tests were used to test the fixed effects and random effects of the three models, and the results showed that the random effects hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, this article chooses fixed effects, and Petersen (2009)^[29] suggests using more effective model estimation methods by clustering through virtual standard errors of individuals and time, to obtain less biased standard errors and more effective estimates. Hence, this article uses fixed effects combined with clustering robust standard error for estimation. In addition to higher efficiency, fixed effects are also designed to handle omitted variable biases in unobserved country heterogeneity and correlation (Wooldridge, 2010)^[30].

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	SD	Min	Max
<i>MTFP</i>	464	1.104	0.415	0.348	3.412

⁵ From: <https://www.fraserinstitute.org/studies/economic-freedom-of-the-world-2020-annual-report>

<i>MTC</i>	464	1.031	0.170	0.777	1.555
<i>MEC</i>	464	1.082	0.417	0.432	4.082
<i>lnSFDI</i>	464	2.418	2.751	-6.817	7.849
<i>HUMAN</i>	464	1.884	0.448	1.137	2.939
<i>TGAP</i>	464	4.647	4.878	0.120	24.663
<i>OPEN</i>	464	0.692	0.818	0.161	7.764
<i>INDUS</i>	464	0.283	0.122	0.094	0.662
<i>GOVC</i>	464	0.385	0.125	0.038	0.745
<i>STAB</i>	464	7.050	1.482	0.000	9.498

Source: Compiled by the author.

Based on the fixed effects model estimation, this paper analyzes the technology spillover effects of China’s OFDI in Africa by controlling for human capital, the technological gap between African countries and China, economic openness, industrial structure, government consumption expenditure, and currency stability.

Table 3 shows the regression results of the model (6,7,8) set in this article. Firstly, from the regression results of all models, it can be seen that, while controlling for other explanatory variables, the coefficient of the technology spillover effect brought about by China’s OFDI, *L.lnSFDI*, is significant and positive at the 1% significance level, that is, it has a positive impact on the changes in total factor productivity (*MTFP*), technological progress (*MTC*), and technological efficiency (*MEC*) of African countries. Column (6) indicates that an increase in standard deviation *L.lnSFDI* per unit (2.751) in the previous year would have a 0.315 percentage point promoting effect on the current year’s *MTFP* ($\frac{\partial MTFP}{\partial SFDI} = 0.115 \cdot 2.751 \approx 0.315$). Furthermore, based on columns (7 and 8), the increase in *L.lnSFDI* from the previous year will have a promoting effect of 0.088 and 0.266 percentage points on the *MTC* and *MEC* of that year, respectively. Therefore, the improvement of total factor productivity in African countries is mainly due to the spillover of China’s OFDI technology to Africa, which has led to the improvement of technology efficiency. This conclusion is consistent with the conclusion of Hu et al. (2021)^[31] who found that China’s OFDI in Africa has a positive and significant impact on the technological efficiency of the region.

Table 3: Regression results of China’s OFDI technology spillover effects on Africa

Model	(6)	(7)	(8)
Variable	<i>MTFP</i>	<i>MTC</i>	<i>MEC</i>
<i>L.lnSFDI</i>	0.115*** (0.018)	0.032*** (0.007)	0.091*** (0.019)
<i>L.HUMAN</i>	0.350* (0.184)	-0.020 (0.070)	0.323* (0.189)
<i>TGAP</i>	0.002 (0.009)	-0.025*** (0.003)	0.030*** (0.009)
<i>OPEN</i>	-0.140** (0.059)	-0.028 (0.022)	-0.098 (0.061)
<i>INDUS</i>	0.465* (0.271)	0.224** (0.102)	0.421 (0.278)
<i>GOVC</i>	0.826***	-0.275***	1.230***

	(0.149)	(0.056)	(0.153)
<i>STAB</i>	0.068***	-0.007	0.073***
	(0.013)	(0.005)	(0.013)
Constant	0.066	1.318***	-0.241
	(0.358)	(0.135)	(0.367)
Obs.	435	435	435
Country effect	YES	YES	YES
Time effect	YES	YES	YES

Note: The parentheses represent standard errors* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Data source: Calculated using Stata17 software.

Secondly, regarding the human capital index *L.HUMAN*, it also has a significant positive effect on total factor productivity⁶ (Column 6), mainly due to the increase in education years and the efficiency of workers in using technology, thereby promoting the growth of total factor productivity. The increase of each unit of *L.HUMAN* in the previous year (0.448) will have a promoting effect on the *MTFP* of the current year by 0.156 percentage points; It will also have a promoting effect of 0.144 percentage points on the *MEC* of that year. However, based on the results of column (7), the coefficient of human capital (i.e. years of education and educational returns) of African countries in this sample on technological progress in the region is negative and has no significant impact. The possible reasons for this phenomenon are: firstly, the human capital level of African countries in the sample is relatively low (i.e. most have less than 9 years of education, and the quality of education itself is still low), and the cost of attending school is a relatively difficult problem for most families to solve; Secondly, many African talents migrate to more developed economies rather than staying in their own countries to make contributions. Therefore, the human capital of African countries is insufficient to promote independent technological innovation, resulting in no significant impact on technological progress.

From the analysis of the technological gap between African countries and China, it can be seen that this variable does not have a significant impact on the total factor productivity of African countries, as its meaning in column (6) is mainly to be applied as a control variable for the core explanatory variable *lnSFDI*. However, this variable is significant at the 1% significance level in column (7) and has a negative impact on technological progress (*MEC*), indicating that the widening technological gap between African countries and China will be detrimental to the technological progress of the host country. Column (8) indicates that *TGAP* is beneficial for promoting the efficiency of technology use in African countries in the sample.

In addition, the economic openness *OPEN* has a significant negative impact on the total factor productivity of African countries at the 1% level and has a significant impact on technological progress and efficiency. Each increase in *OPEN* (0.818) has a negative impact on *MTFP* of -0.114 percentage points. This article believes that the reason for this result is related to the import and export trade structure of Africa, where most African countries are still net importers of manufactured goods and exporters of natural resources. Under this trade structure, the opening up of trade can easily lead to crowding out international investment and have a negative impact on the improvement of total factor productivity in the host country.

Finally, the variables of industrial structure *INDUS*, government consumption expenditure *GOVC*, and currency stability *Stab* all have a positive impact on the total factor productivity (*MTFP*) of African countries, but the distortions caused by non-productive government expenditure and related taxation, as well as changes in fiscal policy stance (*GOVC*), have a negative impact on the technological progress (*MTC*) of African countries.

⁶ This result is consistent with the conclusion of Nondo and Jaramillo (2018), who found that the improvement of human capital quality in African countries has an indirect promoting effect on the improvement of total factor productivity.

5.1. Endogeneity test

Generally speaking, the improvement of total factor productivity can attract more foreign direct investment, thereby promoting the technology spillover effect brought by FDI. On the contrary, the increase of FDI to some extent promotes the total factor productivity of the host country through technology spillover effects. Therefore, there may be a bidirectional causal relationship problem (one of the sources of endogeneity problems), and this article may also be affected by endogeneity problems caused by missing and omitted variables, rationality problems caused by variable measurement methods, and endogeneity problems caused by sample selection. In order to alleviate the endogeneity problem of variable SFDI, this paper uses the classical instrumental variable method for estimation. To ensure unbiased estimation results, two important conditions need to be met when selecting instrumental variables: firstly, the instrumental variables themselves need to be exogenous; Secondly, there is a correlation between instrumental variables and independent variables (endogenous). Therefore, this article first selected two instrumental variables and tested their effectiveness after completing the regression. The first instrumental variable is the SFDI lagged value (referring to Li and Tang, 2019)^[32], and the second instrumental variable is the total trade volume between China and each African country (logarithmic value: *lnTCHN*)⁷. According to many research results, it can be concluded that the total trade volume between China and Africa does not have a direct impact on the total factor productivity of African countries (Miao et al., 2020)^[33]. Therefore, this variable meets the requirements of exogeneity. According to Figure 4, the variable satisfies the second condition (i.e. the correlation condition with endogenous variables).

Fig 4: Scatter plots of variables lnSFDI and lnTCHN from 2003 to 2019

Source: Compiled by the author.

Next, this article estimates the models (6, 7, 8) using the instrumental variable method. From Table 4, it can be seen that the results of the benchmark model are basically consistent with those of the instrumental variable method. The p-value of the Sargan test cannot reject the null hypothesis that the instrumental variables used in the IV regression model are valid, indicating that the instrumental variables selected in this article are exogenous.

Table 4: FE-IV estimation result

Model	(6)	(7)	(8)	FE-IV Method		
				MTFP	MTC	MEC
Variable	<i>MTFP</i>	<i>MTC</i>	<i>MEC</i>	<i>MTFP</i>	<i>MTC</i>	<i>MEC</i>
<i>L. lnSFDI</i>	0.115*** (0.018)	0.032*** (0.007)	0.091*** (0.019)	0.095** (0.011)	0.031*** (0.004)	0.082** (0.012)
<i>L. HUMAN</i>	0.350*	-0.020	0.323*	0.315**	-0.060	0.238*

⁷ This data is sourced from the 2021 United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) database.

	(0.184)	(0.070)	(0.189)	(0.197)	(0.074)	(0.203)
<i>TGAP</i>	0.002	-0.025***	0.030***	-0.004	-0.028***	0.028***
	(0.009)	(0.003)	(0.009)	(0.010)	(0.004)	(0.010)
<i>OPEN</i>	-0.140**	-0.028	-0.098	-0.239***	0.008	-0.240***
	(0.059)	(0.022)	(0.061)	(0.074)	(0.028)	(0.076)
<i>INDUS</i>	0.465*	0.224**	0.421	0.699**	0.354**	0.487*
	(0.271)	(0.102)	(0.278)	(0.281)	(0.105)	(0.289)
<i>GOVC</i>	0.826***	-0.275***	1.230***	0.574***	-0.164***	0.843***
	(0.149)	(0.056)	(0.153)	(0.139)	(0.052)	(0.143)
<i>STAB</i>	0.068***	-0.007	0.073***	0.053***	-0.007	0.057***
	(0.013)	(0.005)	(0.013)	(0.015)	(0.005)	(0.015)
Constant	0.066	1.318***	-0.241			
	(0.358)	(0.135)	(0.367)			
Sargan test P value				0.238	0.146	0.381

Note: The parentheses represent standard errors* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Data source: Calculated using Stata17 software.

5.2. Robustness test

To verify the reliability of indicator selection and empirical methods, robustness tests were conducted on the model after empirical regression. There are many methods for robustness testing, such as changing variable indicators, widening or shortening data samples, and using different regression or estimation methods. This article adopts the third method, using the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS), to ensure the robustness of the regression results. Table 5 shows the estimation results of this method. Obviously, the results estimated by the benchmark model are almost consistent. Therefore, the method adopted in this article can be considered robust.

Table 5: Robustness test

Model	(6)	(7)	(8)	FGLS		
				<i>MTFP</i>	<i>MTC</i>	<i>MEC</i>
<i>L. lnSFDI</i>	0.115***	0.032***	0.091***	0.043***	0.025***	0.032***
	(0.018)	(0.007)	(0.019)	(0.015)	(0.007)	(0.012)
<i>L. HUMAN</i>	0.350*	-0.020	0.323*	0.417***	0.012	0.393***
	(0.184)	(0.070)	(0.189)	(0.161)	(0.072)	(0.114)
<i>TGAP</i>	0.002	-0.025***	0.030***	0.002	-0.026***	0.016***
	(0.009)	(0.003)	(0.009)	(0.005)	(0.004)	(0.006)
<i>OPEN</i>	-0.140**	-0.028	-0.098	-0.048	-0.012	-0.076*
	(0.059)	(0.022)	(0.061)	(0.043)	(0.013)	(0.042)
<i>INDUS</i>	0.465*	0.224**	0.421	0.739**	0.268**	0.370**
	(0.271)	(0.102)	(0.278)	(0.146)	(0.091)	(0.121)
<i>GOVC</i>	0.826***	-0.275***	1.230***	0.201*	-0.087*	0.473***

	(0.149)	(0.056)	(0.153)	(0.108)	(0.046)	(0.085)
STAB	0.068***	-0.007	0.073***	0.029***	-0.003	0.019*
	(0.013)	(0.005)	(0.013)	(0.011)	(0.004)	(0.010)
Constant	0.066	1.318***	-0.241	0.873***	1.204***	0.683***
	(0.358)	(0.135)	(0.367)	(0.270)	(0.114)	(0.186)

Note: The parentheses represent standard errors* p<0.1, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Data source: Calculated using Stata17 software.

6. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

6.1. The main conclusion of this article

The focus of this study is the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa and its influencing factors. The following conclusions are drawn:

(1) China’s direct investment in Africa continues to increase and has a positive impact on the African economy. Firstly, among developing countries, Africa receives less Chinese outward foreign direct investment compared to Western developed countries. However, in the past decade, China’s direct investment in Africa has been increasing, and many studies indicate that this investment has a positive effect on the African economy. In terms of the industries receiving Chinese OFDI in Africa since 2013, the construction industry still holds the first place, with mining and manufacturing industries ranking second and third, respectively. In terms of entry modes for direct investment, greenfield investment remains an important method in Africa. Among the three major investing countries, China is the only one that has not withdrawn its investment.

(2) China’s OFDI in Africa promotes the total factor productivity (TFP) of African countries through technology spillovers. This study employs a two-way fixed effects model to examine the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa. The empirical analysis results demonstrate that the technology spillovers brought by China’s direct investment have a significant promoting effect on Africa’s TFP. At the same time, factors such as human capital, industrial structure, and currency stability also have positive impacts. However, distortions caused by non-productive government spending and related taxes, as well as changes in fiscal policy stance, harm technological progress in African countries. Moreover, the technology gap between African countries and China inhibits the technology spillover effects of China’s direct investment in Africa, while the contribution of African countries’ human capital to these effects is significant.

6.2. Policy Recommendation

Based on the above conclusions, in order to effectively promote economic cooperation between China and Africa and enhance the spill-over benefits of African countries absorbing Chinese OFDI, the following recommendations are proposed:

Firstly, by establishing industrial parks, strengthening cooperation between China and Africa, training local workers, and enhancing the local capacity to absorb technological spillovers. In order to enhance total factor productivity, African governments need to make efforts to develop and promote robust institutions as it will significantly help reduce transaction costs, facilitate resource allocation, and contribute to comprehensive development. Moreover, African countries can encourage more Chinese OFDI to enter labor-intensive manufacturing industries through the establishment of industrial parks. With the rising labor costs in other developing countries, many African countries have a significant advantage in attracting foreign direct investment in labor-intensive manufacturing, which in the long run not only promotes industrialization in host countries but also creates employment opportunities that contribute to economic development.

Secondly, both China and Africa should make joint efforts to foster more technological innovations in their cooperation, aiming for mutual benefits. For the sampled African countries, the lack of technological progress or innovation is evident. Therefore, both sides should jointly encourage the establishment of mechanisms for localized technological transformations to fully utilize technology and promote more innovation in their cooperation. In other words, after direct investment, China should pay more attention to supporting local technological transformations. At the same time, African countries should seek new knowledge and technology from Chinese direct investment to enable them to pursue independent innovation in the future. Additionally, African governments can facilitate technology transfer from foreign companies operating in their countries. This can be done through requirements for local labor and content, backward and forward linkages within the domestic economy, and foreign direct investment activities, thus enhancing the spill-over effects of foreign direct investment.

Thirdly, African countries need to make efforts to improve the investment environment and provide the necessary infrastructure and levels of human capital. Although many countries on the African continent have made considerable efforts to relax their regulations on foreign direct investment and provide incentives to foreign investors, there should be significant and concrete progress in areas such as policy frameworks and infrastructure. Additionally, for the human capital factor, African countries need to undergo certain improvements. Enhancing the overall level of human capital locally is crucial to strengthen the absorption of advanced technologies brought by foreign direct investment and to improve the rate of technological progress. African countries should strive to increase education expenditures, especially in improving basic education, and take specific measures to alleviate the burden of tuition fees for some impoverished families, increase enrollment rates, and extend the duration of education among the population to enhance the level of human capital.

Lastly, in addition to emphasizing China-Africa cooperation, regional economic cooperation among African countries also needs to be further strengthened. The imbalance in efficiency distribution among African countries has led to a decline in overall efficiency. It can be said that there is a considerable productivity gap between different African countries. Furthermore, regional cooperation and institutions are among the determinants of foreign direct investment. Therefore, establishing regional cooperation can serve as a solution to promote overall efficiency balance in investment in Africa. China has significant competitive advantages in cooperation with African countries, and regional economic cooperation can achieve complementarity among nations. The African continent has already begun efforts to improve in this regard and established the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) in 2018. This free trade area was officially launched on January 1, 2021, with 54 out of 55 African Union countries signing the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA). The agreement aims to guide policymakers in formulating and implementing comprehensive reform strategies to achieve substantial returns offered by the agreement.

7. References

- [1] John Whalley, Aaron Weisbrod. The Contribution of Chinese FDI to Africa's Pre-Crisis Growth Surge. *Global Economy Journal*, 2012, 12(4): 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1515/1524-5861.1873>
- [2] Michael. Effect of Chinese Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Growth in Africa. *Special Zone Economy*, 2017: 123-124. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-TAJJ201710034.htm>
- [3] Liu Ailan, Huang Meibo. Analysis of the Impact of China's Direct Investment in Africa. *Journal of International Economic Cooperation*, 2012: 50-55. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-GJJH201202012.htm>
- [4] Donou-Adonsou F., Lim S. On the importance of Chinese investment in Africa. *Review of Development Finance*, 2018, 8(1): 63-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rdf.2018.05.003>
- [5] Liu Yang. The Impact of China's OFDI on African Economic Growth: Based on Panel Data Analysis of 38 African Countries. *Productivity Research*, 2020: 17-19+32. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-SCLY202002005.htm>
- [6] Miao M., Borojo D. G., Yushi J., et al. The impacts of Chinese FDI on domestic investment and economic growth for Africa. *Cogent Business & Management*, 2021, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1886472>
- [7] Zhang K. H. How does South-South FDI affect host economies? Evidence from China-Africa in 2003–2018. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 2021, 75: 690-703. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2021.04.015>
- [8] Yang Zhen. Research on Political Risks and Prevention of China's Direct Investment in Africa. *Times Finance*, 2019: 85-87+89. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-YNJR201908034.htm>
- [9] Fan Zengqiang. The risks faced by Chinese enterprises in non-direct investment and their resolution. *China Business and Market*, 2017, 31: 38-51. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-ZGLT201703005.htm>
- [10] Yuan Qigang, Ji Yongsheng. Political Risk Analysis of China's Direct Investment in Africa. *Journal of Shandong University of Finance and Economics*, 2020, 32: 29-39. <https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/periodical/sdczxyxb202003004>
- [11] Wu Yang, Meng Jiawei. Research on the Dilemma and Countermeasures of Chinese Enterprises in Foreign Direct Investment: A Case Study of Africa. *Times Finance*, 2017: 170-172. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-YNJR201702107.htm>
- [12] An Yongyu. Fifty years of mutually beneficial cooperation between China and Africa with brilliant achievements. *FOREIGN AFFAIRS REVIEW*, 2007. <https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/periodical/wjxyxb200701003>.
- [13] Chen Yanan, Zhao Hong. China Africa Textile Cooperation: Unlimited Prospects. *China WTO Tribune*, 2007, (3): 51-52. <https://qikan.cqvip.com/Qikan/Article/Detail?id=24908480>
- [14] Raphael Z., Zhao C. Africa in China's 'One Belt, One Road' Initiative: A Critical Analysis. *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science*, 2016, 21(12): 10-21. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0837-2112011021>
- [15] G. M Grossman, E. Helpman. Trade, knowledge spillovers, and growth. *European Economic Review*, 1991, 35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(91\)90153-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(91)90153-A)
- [16] D. T. Coe, E. Helpman. International R&D spillovers. *European Economic Review*, 1995, 39(5): 859-887. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(94\)00100-E](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(94)00100-E)
- [17] F. R. Lichtenberg, B. van Pottelsberghe de la Potterie. International R&D spillovers: A comment. *European Economic Review*, 1998, 42(8): 1483-1491. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921\(97\)00089-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921(97)00089-5)
- [18] F. R. Lichtenberg, B. van Pottelsberghe de la Potterie. Does Foreign Direct Investment Transfer Technology Across Borders? *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 2001, 83: 490-497. <https://doi.org/10.1162/00346530152480135>
- [19] A. Razzaq, H. An, S. Delpachitra. Does technology gap increase FDI spillovers on productivity growth? Evidence from Chinese outward FDI in Belt and Road host countries. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 2021, 172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121050>

- [20] Liu Hewang, Zheng Shilin, Zuo Wenting. Research on the Impact Mechanism of Environmental Regulations on Total Factor Productivity of Enterprises. *Science Research Management*, 2016, 37(5): 9. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-KYGL201605005.htm>
- [21] Zhang Jun, Wu Guiying, Zhang Jipeng. Estimation of inter-provincial material capital stock in China: 1952-2000. *Economic Research Journal*, 2004, (10): 10. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-JJYJ200410004.htm>
- [22] Yue Jingui. Technology Spillover Effects Based on Import Trade and FDI Transmission: An Empirical Analysis of Total Factor Productivity in Various Regions of China. *Journal of Economics of Water Resources*, 2008, (02): 7-10+75. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-SLJJ200802002.htm>
- [23] Liu Meiling, Huang Wenjun. Import and export trade, outward direct investment, and international technology spillover effects: an empirical study based on inter-provincial panel data in China from 1999 to 2012. *Journal of Industrial Technological Economics*, 2015, 34(02): 48-54. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-GHZJ201502006.htm>
- [24] Zhao Xinlei, He Rongrong. A Study on the Impact of Interprovincial OFDI in China on Total Factor Productivity from a Spatial Perspective. *Journal of Regional Financial Research*, 2019, (04): 85-91. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-GXJR201904016.htm>
- [25] Robert C Feenstra, Robert Inklaar, Marcel P Timmer. The next generation of the Penn World Table. *American Economic Review*, 2015, 105(10): 3150-3182. <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/aer.20130954>
- [26] H. Wang, H. Liu, Z. Cao, B. Wang. FDI technology spillover and threshold effect of the technology gap: regional differences in the Chinese industrial sector. *Springerplus*, 2016, 5(1): 323. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-1962-6>
- [27] Zhang Zhongyuan, Zhao Guoqing. A Study on the Determinants of FDI Technology Spillover Effect. *Chinese Review of Financial Studies*, 2011, 4: 17. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-JRPL201104010.htm>
- [28] Chen Qifei, Liu Zhibiao. Import Service Trade, Technology Spillover, and Total Factor Productivity: An Empirical Analysis Based on Bilateral Service Trade Data from 47 Countries. *World Economic Papers*, 2015, (05): 1-21. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-SZWH201505001.htm>
- [29] Petersen M. A. Estimating Standard Errors in Finance Panel Data Sets: Comparing Approaches. *Review of Financial Studies*, 2009, 22(1): 435-480. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/hhn053>
- [30] J. M. Wooldridge. *Econometric Analysis of Cross Section and Panel Data, Second Edition*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2010.
- [31] D. F. Hu, K. F. You, B. Esiyok. Foreign direct investment among developing markets and its technological impact on host: Evidence from spatial analysis of Chinese investment in Africa. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 2021, 166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120593>
- [32] Li Jia, Tang Yi. Trade openness, FDI, and total factor productivity. *Macroeconomics*, 2019, (9): 14. <https://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTOTAL-NJSJ201904011.htm>
- [33] M. Miao, J. Yushi, D. G. Borojo. The Impacts of China–Africa Economic Relation on Factor Productivity of African Countries. *Economies*, 2020, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies8020047>

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